

On the Preparation of Some Halogeno-chalkones

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When a halogen atom is introduced in a chalkone in the 2-position so as to result in its conjugation with the α - β -unsaturated carbonyl group system, the resulting compound may possess a high degree of antibacterial activity due to the combined effect of the halogen atom⁴ and the extended conjugation¹⁻³. This has been achieved by the typical synthesis of 2-bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxy-(I), 2-bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-(II), and 2-bromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-chalkones(III). These have been prepared by condensing the appropriate ketones with 2-bromo-4-methyl⁶- and *o*-bromo-benzaldehydes⁶.

These chalkones have been characterised by preparation of their acetates and 2,4-DNP's and also subjected to the Algar-Flynn⁵ oxidation to provide the corresponding flavonols.

2-Bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxychalkone.—To a solution of 2-bromo-4-methylbenzaldehyde⁶ (1.9 g., 0.01*M*) and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone⁷ (1.5 g., 0.01*M*) in ethanol (30 ml) was added in portions freshly prepared 40% KOH solution (6 ml). The mixture was shaken for sometime, the flask corked tightly, and allowed to stand overnight. The condensation product was diluted with water (ice-cold) and acidified with HCl when the chalkone separated as a canary-yellow solid. This was filtered and washed with water. On crystallisation from ethanol 2-bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxychalkone was obtained as canary-yellow, shining, thin rods, m.p. 130°, yield 2.3 g. (Found: Br, 24.79. C₁₆H₁₃O₂Br requires 25.23%). The 2,4-DNP on crystallisation from acetic acid was obtained in orange, rectangular plates, m.p. 234°. The acetyl derivative, prepared by heating the chalkone with acetic anhydride and a few drops of pyridine, melted at 69°.

In the following table are summarised the physical characteristics and analytical data of other chalkones and their derivatives prepared similarly as above.

2'-Bromo-4'-methylflavonol.—2-Bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxychalkone (0.5 g.) in methanol (15 ml) was treated with an aqueous 5% NaOH solution (3 ml) and the mixture cooled to 0°. This was slowly treated with hydrogen peroxide (4 ml, 20 vol.) After the mixture had been allowed to stand overnight in an ice bath, it was diluted with water and acidified with ice-cold H₂SO₄ when the flavonol separated. This was filtered, washed with

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5. *Proc. Roy. Irish Acad.*, 1934, 42B, 1.
6. Jolad and Rajagopal, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 359.
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water, and crystallised from ethanol when 2'-bromo-4'-methylflavonol was obtained as shining, rectangular, thin plates, m.p. 194-95°. (Found: Br, 23.67. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3Br$ requires Br, 24.17%).

TABLE I

Compounds.	Appearance.	M.P.	Formula.	% Bromine.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1. 2-Bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-chalkone	Yellow tiny needles (EtOH)	142°	$C_{17}H_{13}O_3Br$	22.60	23.05
2. Acetyl derivative	Thin flakes (EtOH)	97°			
3. 2,4-DNP	Orange micro-crystals (acetic acid)	243°			
4. 2-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxychalkone	Yellow rectangular flakes (EtOH)	124°	$C_{16}H_{13}O_3Br$	23.65	24.03
5. Acetyl derivative	Shining crystals (EtOH)	120°			
6. 2,4-DNP	Orange micro-crystals (acetic acid)	213-14°			

N. B. Solvent of crystallisation shown in parenthesis.

2-Bromo-4'-methyl-7-methoxyflavonol.—2-Bromo-4-methyl-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-chalkone (0.5 g.) in methanol (9 ml) was treated with an aqueous 5% NaOH solution (2ml) and the mixture cooled to 0°. This was slowly treated with hydrogen peroxide (2ml, 20 vol.). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and worked up as in the preceding case. The product thus obtained was crystallised from ethanol in thin rods, m.p. 159°. (Found: Br, 21.88. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4Br$ requires Br, 22.16%).

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